

Credibility as Informativeness: Predicting Informative Tweets

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Abstract—Social media is an important source of facts at some stage or in any principal event, mainly natural disasters or trends. Since increasingly users take part in numerous social networking services, the extent of streaming information is substantially increasing. It is becoming a big problem to discover informative messages from large amount of data. In this paper we have proposed multi methods to investigate the hassle of detecting informative messages with the data we gathered from Twitter and to classify a tweet into informative and non-informative based on some factors which we found at most important in classification of informative messages. Also, we have proposed an effective technique to solve the classification of Tweets. Most of the data we gathered had a usual behavior which we termed as garbage data which were either a useless tweet, emojis, characters, short foams of sentence, etc. Our work was to overcome these hassles and to calculate the meaningful features which we can describe as one of the most important influence's in classification of tweets in any size of data. This would allow us to normalize our list of features and the accuracy of our Work. Which can increase the probability of informative or non-informative.

Index Terms—Social Media Service, Twitter, Information Filtering, Informative tweets classification.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many of the researcher invested their time in the problem of finding some intimations to able to extract useful information from the text or be able to decide on the basis of data to categorize or label it into informative or non-informative. As the 2020 is passing being able to work with the real time data most of the prefer way is to use Twitter [2] not because of the 300 million monthly active users not including the 145 million daily active users around the globe [3]. One of our reason to utilize twitter in our research is because of the credibility of data is more authentic may be due to the age group as twitter holds 63% of people with the age group of around (35 to 65) years old [3]. It is can also be seen as the one of the most authentic social media platforms as well in contrast to other platforms. Since social media can be seen as the widest range of data where different types of people express their feelings/thoughts to the world to which we can benefit from [1] this type of information which we can gain can benefit us with the different style of information in it. The Problem which we proposed to solve in this paper is to extract meaningful messages/data for not just social media use but to be used in the big scenario applications which do not perform well on unstructured/non-informative data such as, disasters response

application, search engines applications, trend/topic detection programs, recommendation systems. We can take the first path to solve our problem from the twitter's tweet's metadata. As we can see metadata by the unique attributes of each tweets like (Length Of Tweets, No Of Likes, No Of Retweets, No Of Hashtags etc.) [1]. We propose a method for classifying tweet messages into two classes: informative and non-informative [1]. In this paper we have discussed total of three ways to classify informative messages which we termed as Strong (Highly) Informative, Medium and lastly Weak (Low). Which can be seen in the I

A. Categorization of Tweets

All of the three categories rely on some factors which we thought would be very helpful in classifications of the tweets. Strong Informative are those text/tweets which should contain (Some Text, Authentic Source URL, Pictures and Videos) as these entities are very much important to us as they describe the structure of a good informative text. Secondly, we proposed Medium Informative text which relies on the (Some Text, claim of the user). Lastly, we talked about the Weak informative which are only (Pictures and Videos) or unauthentic text (Captions).

We arranged our categories in such a way that the highest priority must be given to the Highly Informative (Combination of authentic source) then on wards with the medium informative (peoples claim) then to the low informative (pictures and videos) in this way we can easily categorise each tweets or to label them with 1 and 0 as Informative and non-informative. Those tweets which do not satisfy our criteria are labeled as non-Informative.

II. RELATED WORK

After searching deeply related to our work we concluded many literature which aim was to find Information in different topics such as [4], Chang discussed about the information based on the user's history on the twitter which is not much helpful to us as it is on only one factor. [5] Some paper also purposed a way in which they categorize the tweets in personalize recommendation way to which they were ranking tweets which in our work was not much appealing as we are

TABLE I
USER BASED FEATURES CORRELATION AND MEAN DISTRIBUTION TABLE

Tweet	Highly Informative	Medium Informative	Low Informative	Non-Informative
Video Shows Chinese Man Converted to Islam By Pak PM Imran Khan's Party https://t.co/vPUOezATar via @ndtv #PTI	1	1	1	0
Pakistan plans to set up 360 MW wind power projects: Imran khan #PTI	0	1	1	0
Let NOBODY Damn disrespect your environment, which you created for your beast level productivity.	0	0	1	0
Let NOBODY#Fun #	0	0	0	1

not concern about the recommendation system. However, we did find something interesting on the [6] Duan research in which they purposed a modal which they talked about the tweet specific features (Likes, URLs, etc.) which we conclude that this path of extracting tweets feature can benefit our modal as the whole information is dependent on the text of the tweets or its [8] metadata. Many of the researches in finding information was dependent on some [7],[9],[10] element such as the Cornelia's paper of social studies concluded the information of the message during the disaster on any sort. Another [9] paper which was somewhat interesting as they were following a specific community, the work of these communities is to like and share the given tweet, although this approach might be helpful in detecting specific topic text but in terms of informative message it might be misleading as those communities can spread non-informative data in social world. Similarly, we came across the work of Konstantinos [1] which elaborated on the extracting feature of each text as to be predict on the basis of some features like (followers, following, Website URLs, etc.) but they were labeling informative as the public trends, interest and event as this can not entirely correct for our work.

III. APPROACH

Our approach to handle the related problems to our research was divided into phases four which were mainly Data generating process, Data Retrieving Process, Data Tagging Process and then lastly Model Preparation which is discussed briefly in this paper. These total process we termed as the System Level Architecture of our project.

A. Data Generating Process

First step for our research we needed to build our local community which consist of different behaviour of people for different curves of data as we do not wanted our data to be bias. This data consists of mainly the age group of 20 to 35 years old, tweeting different types of tweets. This community usually tweets on their own interests also the each user has its own network which is dependent on their followers and following. Total Data set which we generated from this community was approximately 14 thousands lines of data which were further categorized.

B. Data Retrieving Process

Second phase of our architecture was to retrieve the data of our community which we discuss above. The fetching process was done by the twitter API's in JSON format which we merged those individual objects of a person to one data set. From getting each individual object to the single file of users was the main hassle (see user object as JSON format listing: 1). Feature engineering was the next step as this process consist of the tweets feature of different categories such as (NoOfLikes, NoOfHashtags, LegthOfTweet, etc.). Similarly the domain features of the tweet to which domain the tweet belongs to was also categorize further to different sub categories like II (FirstDomainStrength, SecondDomainStrength, ThirdDomainStrength) each tweets contains the strength of the first top three domains out of the total of ten domains which we concluded in the data set III. Lastly we ended on the features of users which we concluded to be very help full in our approach as the user features can express the standard of the tweet, to which we can find the network of the user.

```

1  "source": "<a href=\"http://bufferapp.com\" rel=\"
2  nofollow\">Buffer</a>",
3  "user": {
4    "id": 772682964,
5    "id_str": "772682964",
6    "name": "SitePoint JavaScript",
7    "screen_name": "SitePointJS",
8    "location": "Melbourne, Australia",
9    "description": "Keep up with JavaScript
10   tutorials, tips, tricks and articles at
11   SitePoint.",
12   "url": "http://t.co/cCH13gqeUK",
13   "entities": {
14     "url": {
15       "urls": [{
16         "url": "http://t.co/cCH13gqeUK",
17         "expanded_url": "https://www.sitepoint.com
18         /javascript",
19         "display_url": "sitepoint.com/javascript",
20         "indices": [0, 22]
21       }]
22     },
23     "description": {
24       "urls": []
25     }
26   },
27   "protected": false,
28   "followers_count": 2145,

```

```

25  "friends_count": 18,
26  "listed_count": 328,
27  "created_at": "Wed Aug 22 02:06:33 +0000 2012",
28  "favourites_count": 57,
29  "utc_offset": 43200,
30  "time_zone": "Wellington",
31  },
32  ]]

```

Listing 1. Fetched Data in JSON format

C. Data Tagging Process

This Section will be dependent on the different process of tagging and cleaning of data of the community we discuss above. As our approach was to manually clean the data in which we remove the different language because we did not want any disturbance in the data set by having different language tweets. Our targeted data was purely in English language. We tagged our data-set by our community of people. We specifically told them to tag/annotate each tweet into 3 categories which can be seen in I. The annotators were given supplementary instructions to tag each tweet because some tweet may look like informative but it would not be thoroughly correct. As each tweet is annotated by 5 persons, therefore we had to implement a method for ranking each tagged tweet by the 5 individual. For this requirement to satisfy we used a simple voting system to identify the final tagged tweet information. Each tweet in the data-set is considered to be Informative if it fulfills a specific guidelines which we gave to each individual.

To develop the Ground Truth (GT) about each tweet 1/0 we specified three strategies which we called GT5YES, GT3YES, GTAVG :

- 1) GT-5-YES: In this strategy, If a tweet is marked as YES by every one of the five annotators for the given guidelines, Therefore we annotate this tweet as YES for Information. Otherwise we marked as Non-informative.
- 2) GT-3-YES: If a tweet is marked as YES by every one of the three annotators for the given guidelines, Therefore we annotate this tweet as YES for Information. Otherwise we marked as Non-informative.
- 3) GT-AVG: In this scenario each YES answer is allocated two points and NO answer is allocated zero point. Five annotator's scores are gathered and complete score is calculated. A tweet may have score somewhere between the range of zero and ten points. On the other hand all out score is more than five, Then we annotate this tweet as YES, and in any other case we will label as NO for the given guidelines.

We used this same approach for every category which is strong, medium and low informative

Tweets	GT5yes	GT3yes	GTavg
BREAKING: US Christian pastor freed from Turkish jail, thanks to President Trump's 'key' leadership https://t.co/UVi46dBmXV	1	1	1
So, pleased to hear that the NZ Govt is phasing out single use plastic bags! ripsupb	0	1	1
Sometimes it's best to reach me thru social media, too much be going on.	0	0	1

After going through different researches we decided to divide our total data into three categories for tagging purposes namely, Strong Informative, Medium Informative, Low Informative respectively.

1- Strong Informative: In strong informative our criteria of tagging tweet must have valid Text, authentic URL of any information, valid pictures/picture URL, Videos with authentic source/URL, Hashtags. Here one thing which is most important in Strong Informative is that Valid URL and Informative text must be included in the tweet IV. If the tweet lies on the Strong Informative then it will also be placed in Medium and Low Informative as well.

2- Medium Informative: As most of the researchers related the information on the basis of some news whether the news is authentic or not as describe by Cornelia[]. Similarly we placed a tweet in Medium informative if a someone is claiming some information and which do not have any authentic URL do identify that news and also any facts which can make news authentic then this type of tweet will be placed in the Medium Informative V. Similarly if a tweet is in Medium Informative then it will also be placed in the Low Informative as well.

3- Low Informative: The last category is on the minimum scale of importance for us as these tweets may or may not be informative on the basis of the factors presented on the tweet. We labeled Tweets Low Informative if the tweet has only One entity which can either be only text (Caption or Short Text), Picture URL or Video URL VI.

4- Non-Informative: If any tweet which do not satisfy any of the given category then those tweet will automatically be placed on the non-Informative.

D. Feature Engineering

After the discussion of the data and types of data-set we used, Now we will be talking about the feature engineering and the categories of feature which we divided for clear understatement. We had followed the same approach which we used in data tagging process. Total of three categories were made in each feature entity such as Tweet features, Users feature and lastly Domain features.

TABLE II
TWEET FEATURES WITH TWEET BUT WE ALSO HAVE MORE FEATURES LIKE THIS.

Tweet	Tweet Domain	Number of Hashtags	Number of Mentions	Number of URL's
#digiloi Does any c64 game come close to being as cool as this?	WB	1	0	0
RT @rustyrocks: Mantra meditation. How did you get on? https://t.co/z85ZFShV5Q	PT	0	1	1

TABLE III
USER'S TOP THREE DOMAINS WITH DOMAIN STRENGTHS

Tweet	1st Domain	2nd Domain	3rd Domain	First Strength	Second Strength	Third Strength
Light,fast,and cheep #googlepixelbook http://t.co/AHXMlnlfsk	NW	WB	SP	33.6633	16.83168	12.8712
1st Hourly copies are checked so plz review your answer books today at my office :)	ED	WB	EN	26.2857	16.5714	12.5714

TABLE IV
HOW TWEET BECOME STRONG INFORMATIVE

Tweet	Authentic Text	Authentic Source/URL	Hashtag	Strong Informative
Video Shows Chinese Man Converted to Islam By Pak PM Imran Khan's Party https://t.co/vPUOezATar via @ndtv #PTI	1	1	1	1

TABLE V
MEDIUM INFORMATIVE CONTAINS CLAIM OR FACT BUT NO AUTHENTIC SOURCE AND URL'S .

Tweet	Authentic Text	Authentic Source/URL	Hashtag	Strong Informative
Pakistan plans to set up 360 MW wind power projects: Imran khan PTI	1	0	1	1

Tweet Features: Tweet features consist of many features which related to tweets such as the length of the tweets, No of Hashtags, No of replies, No of Likes, isReply, isRetweeted, No of URL's and the list goes on by this we can find the nature of tweet on the basis of informative. These features of tweets are further more divided into the most important regarding the tweet informative in which we minimize the features by feature selection library from sklearn. Similarly if a tweet represent a URL then its Alexa rank was calculated as well.

User Features: In User Feature we calculated the basic features of any user such as the followers and following count, isVerified, IsDefaultPicture, totalPosts, FriendsCount, totalLikes etc. Some of the features of the User Features are very important as these features can show the level of authenticity of the user and show the level of networks and

spreadness of the tweet

Domain Features: For Domain Features we have total of two sections Particular Tweet Domain Feature and other is User Domain Features. In Domain features we have selected total of ten (10) Domains (e.g: Politics, Well Being, Entertainment, Sports, Science Technology etc.) to which we labeled and used in both the Tweet domain and the user Domain in such a way that each tweet should belong to a specific domain. Similarly a user can tweet about any topic in such a case we extracted the top three (3) Domains in which the user tweeted about.

IV. EVALUATION

A. Characteristics of Datasets

To start the cycle of our research we needed to build the ground truth, as we made the community of our people to annotate into 3 categories which can be seen in Fig: 1 which

TABLE VI
LOW INFORMATIVE DOES NOT CONTAIN ANY CLAIM ANY URL/SOURCE ONLY TEXT LIKE CAPTIONS ...

Tweet	Authentic Text	Authentic Source/URL	Hashtag	Strong Informative
Let NOBODY Damn disrespect your environment, which you created for your beast level productivity.	1	0	0	1

consist of 30 people mainly the friends and their followers in which the total Number of lines of data were 7999. In which Number of Strong Informative are 902 and number Medium Informative 3458 and low Informative 6638 and non-Informative in Strong Informative are 7096, Medium 4542 and Low 1356 respectively.

Fig. 1. This chart base on three categories of features which is Total, Best Gold Feature list ..

B. First Experiment:

Our First experiment begin with the data-set explained above which consist of the 7999 tweets Which is the testing data-set for the experiment for finding the ground truth for best category of Information in Strong, Medium and Low of any information available in the tweet Data, Which can relate the probability of the tweet to be informative or not. Its important to understand here is that although this Data-set is a testing Data for the experiment but it carries all the guidelines of categorization that we discuss in the Approach module.

1- Feature Selection:

First step we needed to define is the Selection of Features as the total Numbers of Features we calculated were about 35 which can be seen in the VIII. In these features we further divided them into two categories which we labeled as Gold Features and Best Features by comparison the Gold features are less then the Best features. Number of Gold Feature are 14 and Best Features are 33 VII here there is an overlap between the Gold Features and Best Feature. Reason to categories the Features list is mainly because of the essentials, meaning the basics which represent the Information in the Tweet/Text.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (f_i - y_i)^2$$

Where N is the number of data points, f_i is the value returned by the model and y_i is the actual value for data point i .

E.g: If a tweet has a bigger network of followers and the No. Re-Tweet rate is high of a tweet then the probability of the Information in the given tweet will be higher.

First we can find results on total feature which contains 35 feature by running on six different models (RANDOM FOREST, LOGISTIC REG, LINEAR SVC , DECISION TREE, GRADIENT BOOST, ADA BOOST) by using 3 different labels (STRONG INFORMATIVE, MEDIUM INFORMATIVE, LOW INFORMATIVE) data-sets which shown in IV-A of the unbalanced data set which will be discuss further. so they shown better results in initial test. Our result clearly indicate that we can more improve our results by different experiments.

2- Different Models Prediction Of Features Categories:

For our first Experiment we included many models to which we feed-ed the features we calculated with different parameters to handle the recoil, miss-classification and also to check the biasness between the training and testing set. The number of models which we commonly used between the categories of information Level of tweets which were Strong Informative, Medium Informative and Low Informative are Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Linear SVC and Extra Tree classifier. In the X we can see that the tagged data which we categories in Strong, Medium and Low were run separately in each models and also the Feature categories were separately annotated to the each tagged data category. After completing this cycle we concluded that the Random Forest performed very well in the classification of tweets X among the other models with minimum miss-classification and best test and training score.

TABLE VII
THIS CHART BASE ON THREE CATEGORIES OF FEATURES WHICH IS TOTAL, BEST GOLD FEATURE LIST

Total Features	Best Features	Gold Features
1.Followers count	1.Followers count	1. No of URLs
2.Friends count	2.Friends count	2. Text length
3.Age of a/c	3.Age of a/c	3. Sentiment Score
4.Is verified	4.Is verified	4. Domain
5.Total no of Posts	5.Total no of Post	5. Tweet Topic
6.Url in profile	6.Url in profile	6. Mention count
7.Desc in profile	7.Desc in profile	7. Retweet count
8.Bot	8.Bot	8. Likes count
9.List Count	9.List Count	9. Hashtag Count
10. Profile Picture(Y/N)	10. Profile Picture(Y/N)	10. Alexa rank
11. Default Profile(Y/N)	11. Default Profile(Y/N)	11. WOT
12. Tweet Domain	12. TweetDomain	12. Age of a/c
13. Retweet count	13. Retweet count	13. Followers count
14. Mention count	14. Mention count	14. Followings count
15. Is reply	15. Is reply	
16. Reputation: Followers/Followers + Followings	16. Reputation	
17. IsRetweet	17. IsRetweet	
18. #Likes	18. #Likes	
19. #URL	19. #URL	
20. WOT Score for URLs	20. WOT Score for URLs	
21. #Swear words	21. #Swear words	
22. #SelfWords(i,my,mine)	22. #SelfWords(i,my,mine)	
23. 1st, 2nd, 3rd Person Pronoun(Y/N)	23. 1st, 2nd, 3rd Person Pronoun(Y/N)	
24. Sentiments: Sub/Obj Score	24. Sentiments: Sub/Obj Score	
25. Text Length	25. Text Length	
26. #words	26. #words	
27. Fraction of upper case letters	27. Fraction of upper case letters	
28. #Hashtags	28. #Hashtags	
29. ?, !, Stock Symbol (\$) (Y/N)	29. ?, !, Stock Symbol (\$) (Y/N)	
30. Reciprocity: friends followers overlap	30. Reciprocity	
31. Post Age(sec)	31. Post Age(sec)	
32. User Domain	32. User Domain	
33. Alexa Rank	33. Alexa rank	
34. Smile & frown icon (:).:(Y/N)		
35. Location		

TABLE VIII
THIS CHART BASE ON THREE CATEGORIES OF FEATURES WHICH IS TOTAL, BEST GOLD FEATURE LIST

Model Name	Total Features			Medium Informative			Low Informative		
	Train acc	Test acc	Miss Classif.	Train acc	Test acc	Miss Classif.	Train acc	Test acc	Miss Classif.
Random Forest	95.54	92.68	48	0.86	0.84	321	95.95	93.29	66
Logistic Reg	76.2	75	112	0.71	0.71	490	0.81	0.78	114
Linear SVC	77.4	76.5	120	0.71	0.71	370	0.81	0.78	114
Decision Tree	98	95.94	64	0.88	0.83	253	1	9	48
Gradient Boost	95.36	93.17	38	82.76	80.2	307	94.97	92.64	29
Ada Boost	96.06	93.05	38	81.81	79	317	95.59	93.84	29

TABLE IX

Model Name	Gold Features Results			Medium Informative			Low Informative		
	Train acc	Test acc	Miss Classif.	Train acc	Test acc	Miss Classif.	Train acc	Test acc	Miss Classif.
Random Forest	0.99	0.92	94	0.85	0.82	363	0.99	0.89	132
Logistic Reg	0.87	0.88	138	0.67	0.68	627	0.82	0.84	182
Linear SVC	0.86	0.88	140	0.67	0.68	626	0.81	0.84	191

The above results which we shared in the X was the result of the 7999 tweets as we can notice that the number of Informative and non-informative are not equal for all of our categories of Strong, Medium and low there for to satisfy the need to equal the amount of Data-Set of each category we balanced the numbers of informative and non-informative respectively for the Best and the Gold feature list. After decreasing the numbers of non-Informative from 7096 to 950 in Strong Informative. Similar for the rest of the both category for the Medium Informative decreasing the non-Informative to 3800 from 4542. Lastly for the Low Informative the number informative were balanced by the 6638 to 1500. After Balancing Data, we again run through this data set on the same model procedures from which we gain a significant change in the result of our three categories of tweets which can be seen in the XI. This was a huge success to our research as we gained significant amount of prediction result on Informative and Non-Informative for the current Data-Set.

After analyzing the results of the above scenario for balanced data set for finding the most suitable category of labeling the tweets for the categories which were Strong, Medium and Low Informative tweets. Through the above mention results we concluded that the result of the Strong Informative were the best among the remaining two categories. For the better approach towards the experiment we will be continuing with the Strong informative category as the Primary category for this research. The main reason for doing the above scenario was to find the ground truth between the three categories which fits the assumption of our tagging criteria as we did not know for sure that which category would perform better in our case.

Now there is only 3 Models which have best AUC-ROC results Which is Random Forest, Decision Tree Classifier and Ada-Boost, and the accuracy is about 0.94 AUC which is really considerable at this point. Which Shown in 2

C. Second Experiment:

Before beginning with the second phase with the experiment as the data-set we used in the above experiment was used for each of the three categories but in this experiment we will be generating new data-set which were based on 11140 number of lines which contain 6428 informative and 4712 non-informative tweets which we will be used for the remaining part of the experiment. For our main research we will be using the above data-set. as this data-set will only be using Strong Informative category for our experiment.

More realistic reason for this data-set to be used was purely for the balancing of data. From the graph above we can quickly observe by looking at this data-set directly we can judge that the above data-set is more balanced and equally biased and the experiment of categorization by features discuss in the (Section

D) will be performed as well with same techniques use and method for the differences and the reality of our research. But in this experiment as we concluded in **First Experiment** we extracted that the best result were generated by **Strong Informative** tweets, Therefore in this experiment we will only be using Strong Informative.

D. EXPLORATORY DATA ANALYSIS:

After extraction of information/data and tagging, pre-processing of data, Exploratory Data Analysis is a major role, where the information/data is plainly envisioned, plotted, handle, with no point of supposition, to help decide the nature of the facts and figures and building models. Therefore for the exploratory facts examination we change our information in to binary class classifications of data.

In this paper, we have applied bi-variate examination to discover the features which are significant in the feature list, correspond in foreseeing the yield and plainly portraying the example of data.

For the bi-variate examination we have to plot, Box plot (Box plots are fascinating for addressing data about the focal propensity, outliers, slant and evenness), KDE (kernel density estimate shows the data in at least one measurements utilizing a nonstop likelihood density bend) and ECDF (Empirical Cumulative Distribution Function empowers you to fundamentally plot a component of your information from the least to the biggest and consider to be include as though it were conveyed through the data group). On the binary classification of data we had applied bi-variate analysis.

As demonstrated in the figures underneath highlights are indicating the diverse example for the Informative and non-Informative.

In the following lists of comparison we analyzed different features through bi-variate analysis. In which we did an Exploratory Data Analysis which simply give the glance of the data fed to it for the better understatement of position or summary of data. Usually this includes Histogram for the statics and also the scattered plots to find the core-relation between the features of the data. Coming back to Estimator of the Cumulative Distribution Function (ECDF) which can make a plot of features for the given data same as given below, In least to greatest order and enable to see the whole features as it is distributed across the provided data set. In our case we discovered that the leangth of tweet and top first domain were extracted as the most important features for the ECDF.

1) *Feature Analysis using ECDF:* For the experiment we have used t-sne (t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding) also called as dimensionality reduction algorithm. The main concept of t-sne algorithm is to separate data that can't be distinguish by any straight line as you can see the t-sne plot of all features that we cannot easily distinguish data by any straight line but as comapare to t-sne plot of selected features it is possible to distinguish data through some line.

TABLE X
 THE RESULTS OF UNBALANCED DATA-SET(A), IN THIS FIG WE CAN SHOW BOTH CATEGORIES RESULT (GOLD AND BEST). AND ALSO HIGHLIGHT THE BEST RESULTS IN BOTH CATEGORIES

Best Features Results									
	Strong Informative			Medium Informative			Low Informative		
Model Name	Train acc	Test acc	Miss Classif.	Train acc	Test acc	Miss Classif.	Train acc	Test acc	Miss Classif.
Random Forest	0.99	0.9	118	0.83	0.81	217	0.99	0.89	131
Logistic Reg	0.87	0.87	142	0.69	0.69	349	0.85	0.87	142
Linear SVC	0.87	0.87	143	0.69	0.68	359	0.85	0.87	145

TABLE XI

Best Features Results									
	Strong Informative			Medium Informative			Low Informative		
Model Name	Train acc	Test acc	Miss Classif.	Train acc	Test acc	Miss Classif.	Train acc	Test acc	Miss Classif.
Random Forest	96.94	93.98	28	0.85	0.83	341	96.95	94.29	86
Logistic Reg	77	76	105	0.7	0.7	560	0.81	0.79	124
Linear SVC	78.4	77.5	100	0.7	0.7	570	0.81	0.79	124
Decision Tree	99	94.94	24	0.85	0.81	353	1	9	36
Gradient Boost	96.36	94.07	26	82.96	80.52	377	95.97	93.64	39
Ada Boost	96.86	93.75	38	81.71	80	387	96.79	93.64	39

TABLE XII
 BALANCED DATA-SET BEST AND GOLD FEATURES. WE CAN BALANCE THE DATA BY ADDING SOME INFORMATIVE TWEETS DATA-SET AND FIND BETTER RESULTS

Gold Features Results									
	Strong Informative			Medium Informative			Low Informative		
Model Name	Train acc	Test acc	Miss Classif.	Train acc	Test acc	Miss Classif.	Train acc	Test acc	Miss Classif.
Random Forest	96.43	94.33	27	94.78	91.16	157	96.69	93.72	45
Logistic Reg	0.91	0.92	34	0.84	0.85	265	0.7	0.72	196
Linear SVC	0.9	0.92	34	0.84	0.84	269	0.69	0.72	199
Decision Tree	1	0.94	24	0.99	0.9	161	0.99	0.93	46
Gradient Boost	96.57	94.12	28	91.52	90.32	172	94.55	93.44	47

Fig. 2. AUC-ROC First Experiment

Fig. 3. ..

2) *Feature Analysis using TSNE*: We plot co-variance matrix to analyze the correlation between features that how much correlated with each others. If correlation between two features is more than 0.9 then it is said to be highly correlated, as you can see in figure () that correlation between lengthoftweet feature and wordCount feature is more than 0.9 then this features are highly correlated with each other and other features like listedCount and followersCount are also highly correlated with each other. If features having correlation between 0.5 to 0.89 said to be correlated like listedCount and TotalPost feature are correlated. Similarly if the feature value in the co-varient matrix are lower then the 0.5 then for those features we will say as low correlation such as he features friendsCount followersCount and many more presented in the below plot, For the features who have their values negative are called negative correlation such as the features favouriteCountOfThe User and the URLsCount.

E. Feature Selection

For clarity of selecting the best features list for our scenario we have performed a unique technique for minimizing the feature list accordingly. Such that we do not lose any prediction results and performance of the model while shortening the feature list. To overcome this situation we made a co-variance matrix which shows co-relation between features and also the selected features through ECDF (reference in EDA) feature selection through models. If we see in XIII example below. we have used this techniques for feature selection.

1) *Feature Selection Through Models*: To determine the the ground reality of most important feature for some models we further implemented an experiment of selecting top nine (9) features list from the given models of Cat Boost, Decision Tree, Gradient Boost, Lasso, Logistic Regression, Random Forest, Ridge and finally XG Boost. If we talked about the list of each models then there are some of the common features selected by the each models of the eight models which were first-Strength and second-Strength and then num-urls, LengthOftweet, createdAt, first-tag, Total-Post, num-hashtag, third-tag, WordCount, BotoMeter and Follower-Count were present in the 5 different models of (CatBoost, DecisionTree, GradientBoost, Lasso, Logistic, RandForest, Ridge and XG-Boost). In CatBoost total number of selected features

TABLE XIII
FEATURE SELECTION BY MODELS: THIS FEATURES ARE SELECT BY DIFFERENT MODELS AND WE ARRANGED ALL FEATURES ACCORDING TO THE PRIORITY

Feature Selection through Multiple models	Priority
firststrength	Very High
thirdstrength	Very High
numurls	High
LengthOfTweet	High
Created_at	High
firsttag	High
TotalPosts	High
numhashtags	High
thridtag	High
WordCount	High
Bot	High
followerscount	High
friendscount	Medium
UpperCaseCount	Medium
favouritecount	Medium
SpecialCharacters	Medium
secondstrength	Medium
retweetcount	Medium
DefaultProfile	Low
Tweet_Domain	Low
IstPersonPronoun	Low
ListCount	Low
secondtag	Low

by the models it self are 8, Similarly, Ridge covers the most extended features list in comparison from the above four models it selected the total of 31 of feature's from the total feature list (**Fig- 9**), Decision Tree selected total of 8 features and Gradient Boost selected total of 8 features from the list, lasso comes second in-terms of the most feature selection which were 26, Finally Logistic and Random Forest selected 19 and 15 respectively. In our view by comparing the results and the shorten features list were in ada Boost, Cat Boost, Decison Tree and Gradient Boost were the one which selected minimum number of features among the above nine (9) models in comparison of Random Forest, Lasso, Logistic Regression, Ridge and finally XG Boost.. The Above Scenario of features can be seen in the below figures

2) *Feature Ranking*: To start with the feature ranking, we had applied many of the different and distinctive ML Models to discover which features holds most importance in our scenario. At that point we managed each features list for each models in descending order in sliding request regarding feature significance. Then we extracted the best performing features in the applied feature model list.

After that we check the situation of the feature in different models and compose it in the section of that specific model. Next we take away the specific position from the all out number of highlights in top entertainer model. After that we

Fig. 4. Feature Analysis using ECDF

Fig. 5. tSNE Plot using All Features

Fig. 6. TSNE Plot using Selected Features

Fig. 7. 1st Person Tag

Fig. 8. 3rd Person Tag

Fig. 9. Domain

Fig. 10. Retweet Count

Fig. 11. Sentiment Analysis

Fig. 12. Special Character

Fig. 13. Word Count Analysis

TABLE XIV
RANK OF FEATURE THROUGH EVERY MODEL

Model Name	Feature Rank
Botometer	
Lasso	11
Ridge	16
Decision Tree Classifier	13
Random forest Regressor	12
Gradient Boost Regressor	7
AdaBoost Regressor	14
XG Boost Regressor	13
CatBoost Regressor	15
Logistic Regression	16

add all the positions for the specific feature. At long last we orchestrate the feature in descending order in the light of the feature ranking. For instance: Let 'BotoMeter' is the primary element of the top entertainer Gradient Boost model and all out number of highlight given by Gradient Boost are 35, Therefore for ranking of the selected feature can be seen below with examples.

- Here We have ranked the feature we selected in different ML models as you can see XIV which we have used commonly in the experiment and if there is no score given by the model then we will leave it as blank.
- For the second step as you can see XV we will be extracting the total numbers of features selected by the Gradient Boost which were 35 with the above list.
- Then for the final step we added all the total numbers of all models for the final rank of the feature 'BotoMeter' see 14.

For the sum up of the Feature ranking of the 'BotoMeter' feature were calculated as 198. Like this we locate the positioning of each feature present in the most important features list given by the Gradient Boost model. Subsequent to finding the ranking of each feature we organize them in descending

TABLE XV
SELECTION OF RANK OF BEST MODEL AND SUBTRACT OTHER MODEL THROUGH IT

Model Name	Feature Rank
Botometer	
Lasso	35-11=24
Ridge	35-16=19
Decision Tree Classifier	35-13=22
Random forest Regressor	35-12=23
Gradient Boost Regressor	35-7=28
AdaBoost Regressor	35-14=21
XG Boost Regressor	35-13=22
CatBoost Regressor	35-15=20
Logistic Regression	35-16=19

TABLE XVI
FINALIZING RANK BY ADDING ALL NUMBERS

Features	Rank
BotoMeter	24+19+22+23+28+21+22+20+19=198

request as for their feature significance as demonstrated in the figure below in XVII.

In the Correlation and value distribution table we have manage a technique for useful feature from the two list labeled as (A) and (B) in list. Where (A) is the mean of the feature through uni-variant analysis and (B) is the Correlation between the features. After extraction of the both list we simply applied OR between the list and made a new list to which our experiment was successful as the results were better then the previous result. The main soul of this experiment was to find the most important feature list for the case of informative extraction from a tweet, to which we performed four main sub-experiments which were 1) Feature Selection through models shown in Table: XIII, 2) Through Feature Ranking shown in Table: XVII 3) Through Correlation shown in Table: XVIII, and finally 4) Through ECDF. All of the above experiments clearly show the scenarios of most significant features to the cause of the paper and to justify all of the each the selected features by the experiments we can proof that our selected features are present in the top 15 features in the **Feature Selection through models and Feature Ranking List**. Coming back to the results we concluded below form the all feature list from directly comparing to the Correlation results list that performance of the models were not much effected by minimizing the feature list and the results of the models as well. From **35** features to **12** list features road was the main success for this paper and the whole experiment in this section seen in Table: XIX. In fact the results of the Correlation selected features were significantly improved in almost all of the features with minimum Miss-Classification as well as the increase in the Precision's. By applying multiple models in the 35 features list we observed that the best result we gained through Gradient Boost with minimum Miss-Classification and Maximum Recall and Precision see in Table:

Fig. 14. Co-variance Matrix

Fig. 15. Features Selected by Different Models

Fig. 16. ROC AUC of All Features

XX.

In the table of Table: XXI (Results of Selected Features), We again ran the same multiple models but with **12** features list from which we gained significant achievement by comparison of the total features list of **35**. Again the best performing model were Gradient Boost without effecting much with the previous result but significant reduce in the feature list which were the ground reality of the experiment.

V. FUTURE DIRECTION AND CONCLUSION

This paper developed a method for detecting the informative and non-informative tweets and described in-depth knowledge in extraction of features according to the situation. It is observed that the proposed method given in this paper performed better and will also increase the level of the accuracy if provided more accurate data under the given guidelines of categorization of tweets and special features which this paper

TABLE XVII

IN THIS TABLE WE CAN ARRANGE FEATURES ACCORDING TO RANKS

S.No	Features	Rank
1	first_tag	209
2	first_strength	183
3	third_strength	180
4	num_urls	179
5	num_hashtags	139
6	LengthOfTweet	125
7	TotalPosts	112
8	followers_count	110
9	Tweet_Domain	110
10	UpperCaseCount	109
11	Bot	108
12	favourite_count	105
13	created_at	101
14	WordCount	100
15	second_tag	95
16	favourites_count	89
17	List_Count	78
18	thrid_tag	76
19	friends_count	67
20	SpecialCharacter	65
21	second_strength	64
22	retweet_count	49
23	Desc in Profile (Y/N)	47
24	num_mentions	33
25	Sentiment score	27

Fig. 17. ROC AUC of Selected Features

No Skill: ROC AUC=0.500
 Logistic: ROC AUC=0.999

defined then using the other methods for tweet categorization such as the information based on the user's history on the twitter. In future, it can extended for other data-sets. The method can be improved by adding more layers and applying other deep learning methods.

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TABLE XVIII
FEATURE SELECTION THROUGH CORRELATION AND VALUE DISTRIBUTION

SR#	FEATURE NAME	Informative	Non- Informative	C1	C2	C3	C4
1	top_first_domain strength	68.342	59.373	Yes	2,11	Yes (Replace 2,11)	Yes
2	top_third_domain strength	7.144	10.34252	Yes	1	Yes	Yes
3	urls_count	1.0491	0.5628	Yes	8, 16	Yes	Yes
4	Hashtag_count	0.21	0.32	YES		NO	YES
5	LengthOfTweet	99.83	44.968	Yes	12	Yes	Yes
6	TotalPost	11989.19	11837.04	Yes	14, 7, 2, 15, 10	Yes (Replace 7, 14, 15, 1)	Yes
7	followers_count	593.52	824.187	YES	6	NO (Removed by 6)	Yes
8	UpperCaseCount	11.95	5.454	Yes	3	NO (Removed by 3)	Yes
9	Botometer	1.360	1.090	NO		NO	NO
10	User's_favorite count	2960.02	5628.84	Yes	6	NO (Removed by 6)	Yes
11	Created_at	1.4e+08	1.07e+08	NO	1	NO (Removed by 1)	NO
12	Wordcount	13.123	5.67	Yes	5,14	Yes (Replace 5, 14)	Yes
13	Top_Second_Domain	0.34	0.42	NO		NO	NO
14	List_count	22.35	23.94	NO	12	NO (Removed by 6)	NO
15	Friends_count	11523.061	1130.311	Yes	6	NO (Removed by 3)	Yes
16	Top_Second_Domain_Strength	16.18	18.31	NO	3	Yes (No Corr)	Yes
17	Retweet_count	1	0.219	Yes		Yes (No Corr)	Yes
18	Mentions_count	0.449	0.494	NO		(No Corr)	NO

TABLE XIX
BEST SELECTED FEATURE

Selected Features
WordCount
UpperCase_letter_count
TotalPost
Top_First_domain_Strength
Follower_count
Favourites_count
Urls_count
Top_Third_Domain_strength
LengthOfTweet
Retweet_Count
Friends_Count
Top_First_Domain

TABLE XX
RESULTS OF ALL FEATURES LIST

S.No	Algorithm	Train Acc	Test Acc	Precision	Recall	Miss Classification
1	Logistic Regression	61.12	62.15	62.87	57.09	1265
2	Linear SVC	70.07	71.36	72.23	72.59	957
3	Decision Tree	100.00	99.49	99.49	99.46	17
4	Random Forest	99.79	99.37	99.40	99.31	21
5	GB Boost	99.92	99.82	99.82	99.82	6
6	Ada Boost	100.00	99.49	99.51	99.45	17
7	Cat Boost	99.79	99.64	99.62	99.64	12
8	XG Boost	98.78	98.65	98.64	98.60	46

TABLE XXI
RESULTS OF SELECTED FEATURES

S.No	Algorithm	Train Acc	Test Acc	Precision	Recall	Miss Classification
1	Logistic Regression	85.56	85.31	84.96	84.94	491
2	Linear SVC	75.67	75.82	76.78	77.19	808
3	Decision Tree	99.99	98.86	98.82	98.85	38
4	Random Forest	99.65	99.13	99.13	99.09	29
5	GB Boost	99.56	99.37	99.37	99.34	21
6	Ada Boost	99.99	99.16	99.12	99.16	28
7	Cat Boost	99.41	99.31	99.30	99.29	23
8	XG Boost	96.54	96.23	96.14	96.14	126